

Unidentified species of *Longidorus* and *Xiphinema* were also occasionally found.

All three known nematode parasites of rice — *M. graminicola*, *H. oryzae*, and *T. martini* — probably cause significant yield reductions in deepwater rice in Bangladesh. *M. graminicola* root-knot nematode probably causes the most

damage to the aman crop. Typical field symptoms are yellowing and stunting, associated with the presence of *M. graminicola* females within roots and with some galling. *M. graminicola* can obviously tolerate flooding — large numbers of it were found in roots submerged in water as deep as 1.5 m, which was expected to reach more than

4-m depth later. The soil temperatures at the sites ranged from 31 to 36°C. The main *M. graminicola* damage appeared to be reduction in the ability of the deepwater rice plant to elongate so that it could not keep pace with the rising floodwater. In some situations, that could result in the complete drowning out of the crop. ■

Synergy between benomyl and carbofuran in the control of ufra

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Ufra (caused by the stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* Filipjev) is a serious disease of deepwater rice in southern Bangladesh. During 1978, an experiment on its chemical control when symptoms appear in the vegetative phase was laid out at a study site in Comilla District. A treated plot was arranged on each edge of a square untreated control plot to form a cross. All plots were 5 m x 5 m. The design reduced edge effects between treated plots as no two were contiguous along a boundary. Patchiness in disease distribution was also reduced as each treated plot was equidistant from the control and was surrounded by an untreated area. Four treatments were allocated randomly to the outer plots (see table). There were three replications in different fields. All were harvested in November.

Chemicals were applied in mid-August (soon after the appearance of chlorosis

Yield of rough rice at three sites with chemical treatment with carbofuran (F) and benomyl (B) after the appearance of symptoms of ufra attack in the vegetative phase.

Treatment ^a	Yield of rough rice (t/ha at 14% moisture)				
	Block 1	Block 2	Block 3	Treatment totals	Treatment means ^b
F + B	1.54	1.53	1.86	4.93	1.64 ± 0.13 a
F + F	1.38	1.40	0.90	3.68	1.23 ± 0.13 ab
B + F	1.11	1.32	0.94	3.37	1.12 ± 0.13 bc
B + B	0.98	0.67	0.73	2.38	0.79 ± 0.13 cd
Control	0.45	0.96	0.61	2.02	0.67 ± 0.13 d
Block totals	5.46	5.88	5.04	16.38	1.09

^aThe first letter of each treatment represents application in mid-August; the second letter, application in early October.

^bAny two means having a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

and distortion of the young leaves) and just before panicle initiation in early October. Carbofuran, a granular insecticide, was applied to the floodwater (about 0.5 m deep) as Furadan 3G at 2 kg/m². Benomyl, a systemic fungicide, was applied to the foliage with a knapsack sprayer as Benlate 50 WP at 12.5 g/25 m². Since it is easier to detect synergy between two chemicals when the marginal physical product of one of them approaches zero, a high rate of carbofuran was necessary.

The analysis of variance indicates a significant difference between treatment effects (p<0.01). Two applications of benomyl did not give a significant yield

improvement. The three other treatment means were significantly different from the mean of the control plot (p<0.05). The significant difference between F + B and B + F may be explained either by the diminishing effect of carbofuran or an augmented effect of benomyl, as the time of application was postponed. There is evidence of a synergistic interaction between carbofuran and benomyl in the control of ufra. Although two applications of benomyl were less effective than two applications of carbofuran, carbofuran was less effective than benomyl after an initial carbofuran application. ■

Pest management and control DISEASES

Efficiency of granular herbicides and cultural methods in rice weed control

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Granular forms of 2 esters (isopropyl and ethyl of 2,4-D at 1.0 and 1.5 kg a.i./ha were compared for

efficiency in weed control with butachlor (G) at 2 kg/ha, nitrofen (G) at 2.0 kg/ha, propanil at 3.0 liters + 2,4-D Na salt at 0.8 kg a.i./ha, two hand weedings, a weed-free check, and an unweeded control in 1978 kharif. The weed flora in the experimental field included *Echinochloa colonum*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Cyperus* spp., *Fimbristylis* spp.,

Ammania baccifera, *Ludwigia* spp., *Eclipta alba*, *Monochoria vaginalis*, *Potamogeton*, and *Anagallis arvensis*. The butachlor treatment had the lowest weed count, followed by 2,4-D EE at 1.5 kg/ha. The dry weight of weeds was lowest with 2,4-D IPE at 1.5 kg/ha — statistically the same level as that with 2,4-D IPE at 1.0, 2,4-D EE at 1.5 and